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More Imitative Trajan Sestertii from Britain:
Additional Evidence for the 'Modius Group' and
Other Finds

by

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More Imitative Trajan Sestertii from Britain: Additional Evidence for the ‘*Modius* Group’ and Other Finds¹

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[PLATES 14-16]

IN TWO articles in volumes 170 and 173 of this journal,² a group of four closely die-linked imitative sestertii with portraits of Trajan was reconstructed (here **Pl. 14, 1–4**). Two of these four coins had surfaced in trade, while the other two are documented English site finds from Somerset and Norfolk, recorded through the Portable Antiquities Scheme (PAS): the entire group may thus confidently be presumed to be of Romano-British production. In the present note, two additional sestertii of this group will be published, which were recently re-discovered in the Heberden Coin Room of the Ashmolean Museum (Oxford) by Jérôme Mairat. Furthermore, a new ‘pseudo-Trajanic’ find from Norfolk as well as an interesting imitative middle bronze from the French trade will be presented.

The four sestertii of the group under consideration hitherto known to me were struck from two obverse and two reverse dies. The obverse dies are characterised by a nearly official-looking portrait of the emperor and an almost impeccable legend of the COS V period, whereas the reverse dies clearly mark out these pieces as imitative, since their types do not have parallels in the regular imperial coinage of Trajan: one die does not bear a design, but merely the legend SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI and a large S C (**Pl. 14, 1**), while the other has a *modius* with corn ears, flanked by the letters S–C. On this die, perhaps copying Nerva’s PLEBEI VRBANAE FRUMENTO CONSTITVTO sestertii (**Pl. 15, 7**),³ there is a garbled and retrograde version of the SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI inscription (**Pl. 14, 2–4** and **Pl. 16, 4a**).

One of the coins re-discovered some months ago in the so-called ‘Evans Duplicates Cabinet’ of the Heberden Coin Room was struck from this same reverse die, but from a different obverse die:

¹ Thanks are due to Jérôme Mairat (Oxford) for directing my attention to the sestertii of the ‘*modius* group’ in the Ashmolean Museum and to Adrian Marsden (Norwich) for informing me about the newly found Marham sestertius as well as for generously making it available for study.

² B.E. Woytek, ‘A new ‘Trajanic’ sestertius from Somerset and its context: some general remarks on struck copies of imperial bronze coins of Trajan’, *NC* 170 (2010), pp. 115–28; ‘Further imitations of Trajanic bronze coins from Britain’, *NC* 173 (2013), pp. 99–104.

³ *RIC* Nerva 89 and 103.

Imitative Sestertius

Obv.]O NG GER D[

Laureate bust of Trajan right (one of the two wreath ties floating, the other on the shoulder), stylised drapery on left shoulder.

Rev. SDOP [OPTIAAO P]PINDIPI (retrograde; legend starting at 4 o'clock)

S – C (in left and right fields)

Rectangular *modius* (on four feet) with seven stylised corn ears/poppies. Exergual line.

Weight 20.10g; 7h; diameter 32mm.

Oxford, Ashmolean Museum, Heberden Coin Room (Evans Duplicates Cabinet).

Pl. 14, 5

This coin is in rather poor condition, but despite the considerable wear and the damage to the surface on the reverse it is clear that the reverse die is the same as the one used to strike the coins depicted on **Pl. 14, 2–4**. However, when this piece was produced, the die was already in a rather bad state: die breaks between the S as well as the C of the S – C and the *modius* are in evidence. This is in line with observations made for one of the obverse dies of the group: a large break on the die illustrated at **Pl. 14, 1–2** and **4** (as well as **Pl. 16, 4a**) makes it clear that this issue was struck quite carelessly, and the use of the dies – which may have been of rather low quality from a technological point of view – seems to have continued as long as possible, even after damage had occurred. The obverse die of the Oxford specimen is new, and it is through this die that another piece in the Ashmolean Museum is connected to the imitative ‘*modius* group’. Fortunately, this sestertius is much better preserved.

Imitative Sestertius

Obv.]AIANO NG GER DAC P M TR P COS V[

Laureate bust of Trajan right (one of the two wreath ties floating, the other on the shoulder), stylised drapery on left shoulder.

Rev. SROR OPTIAAO [?] PINOPI (retrograde; legend starting at 4 o'clock)

S – C (in left and right fields)

Trapezoidal *modius* (on four feet), with a decorative line border, a horizontal border in the centre (barely visible) and with seven stylised corn ears/poppies. Exergual line.

Dotted border.

Weight 25.71g; 10h; diameter 34mm.

Oxford, Ashmolean Museum, Heberden Coin Room (Evans Duplicates Cabinet).

Ex Glendining & Co., auction sale 16 November 1950 (Henry Platt Hall collection, part II), no. 1331 (together with two sestertii of Trajan; described “*rev. modius, barbarous work*”, not illustrated in the catalogue).

The ticket of Henry Platt Hall is preserved, indicating that he bought this coin on 14 June 1898 from Baldwin’s.

Pl. 14, 6 and Pl. 16, 6a

The obverse die of the two Oxford pieces differs remarkably from the two obverse dies attested for this group up to now. The hair, drapery, knot and wreath ties are

much more stylised on this die, and the overall impression of the portrait is much more ‘barbarous’, with perhaps only the pointed chin and the treatment of the mouth providing parallels to the portraits hitherto known. The bust variety (a cloak on the far shoulder) is, however, the same as on the two other dies, and there is a marked truncation here, too – albeit of a completely different shape. Apart from a minor blunder (NG instead of AVG), this die’s legend seems to be correct, as far as it can be read, and this connects the new die to the other two. At first sight it may seem surprising to see dies of completely different artistic quality being used in the very same group, but in fact this does sometimes occur in imitative coinages; the two hitherto known reverse dies of this group – one with an orthodox legend (**Pl. 14, 1**), the other with a garbled and retrograde one (**Pl. 14, 2–4**) – provide evidence for the same phenomenon. Occasionally, even the obverse and reverse of the very same coin exhibit considerable differences regarding their style, as may be seen from a recently discovered imitative sestertius from Britain discussed below.

The reverse die of the specimen from the H. Platt Hall collection is attested here for the first time. It is quite remarkable in that both the legend and the image are extremely close to the *modius* die of the group known up to now, although the two dies are clearly not identical (see **Pl. 16, 4a** and **6a**). The most striking parallels may be observed in the legends. On each die, there is a bold S–C, and both of these letters have prominent serifs. The retrograde inscriptions start at about 4 o’clock in both cases, and the sequence of letters is the same, with just the second and fourth letters differing a little in shape. The M in OPTIMO is identically split up into two lambda-shaped elements (ΛΛ) on both dies. Perhaps the most telling analogy between the two dies is to be found in the first letter of the main legend, the S of the somewhat deformed SPQR. On both dies, the top of this letter is not pointing outward, but the entire letter is rotated 90 degrees clockwise, as compared to the other retrograde letters of the legend. This means that when looking at the coin (with the top of its reverse design being at 12h), the viewer in fact does not see a retrograde, but a small orthodox upright S at 4 o’clock.

It is thus evident that one of the two imitative *modius* dies must have been copied from the other. The slightly trapezoidal shape of the *modius* (in side view) on the die of the Platt Hall specimen is more akin to the shape of the *modius* on the Nerva prototype, and just as on these PLEBEI VRBANAЕ FRUMENTO CONSTITVTO pieces, the stalks of the corn ears/poppies are markedly bent to the left and to the right here, as opposed to the stalks on the imitative die previously known (**Pl. 16, 4a** and **6a**). Hence, the die of the Platt Hall specimen may be presumed to have been cut earlier and probably served as a model for the other die. There is no evidence for the findspot of the Platt Hall sestertius, but the fact that the collector acquired it from a London dealer in 1898 is consonant with the documented British origin of other coins in this group. Currently, a total of six specimens, all die-linked, from three obverse and three reverse dies are known. This makes the ‘*modius* group’ by far the largest die-linked ensemble of imitative sestertii with Trajanic types known to me. More coins doubtless remain to be discovered, whether in the ground or in (British) collections.

In my 2013 contribution on the topic, I published three imitative Trajan sestertii recorded by Adrian Marsden (Norwich), who kindly also sent me the following specimen for inspection.

Imitative Sestertius

Obv. IMP [...]RAIANO AVG GER DAC P M TR P C[O]S V P P

Laureate bust of Trajan right (both wreath ties falling down the emperor's neck), drapery on left shoulder.

Rev. SPQRO[

S C (in exergue)

Female figure, draped, seated to the left on throne with high square back, extending her right hand in which she holds an uncertain object – perhaps a *patera* – and resting her left elbow on the throne. Her right lower leg is thin and curved. The lower part of the throne is decorated with two crescent-shaped objects.

Weight 23.22g; 5h; diameter 33mm.

Found at Marham in Norfolk by Ian Goodger of King's Lynn Metal Detecting Club in late December 2013 or early January 2014.

Portable Antiquities Scheme database no. NMS-0FF7D6.

Norfolk Historic Environment Record (HER) no. 29189.

Pl. 15, 8 and **Pl. 16, 8a**

While the obverse of this piece is near-impeccable, its reverse featuring a female figure (whose bosom is in evidence) is clearly irregular. The model might *prima vista* be thought to be Pax seated to the left, a type very frequent on Trajanic sestertii of the period AD 98–103/104.⁴ This personification, however, usually holds a transverse sceptre in her left hand, which is not present here. Admittedly, it might have been left out by the craftsman who produced the reverse die for these coins,⁵ but there is another problem: what remains of the reverse legend of the imitation was clearly copied from the classic Trajanic reverse inscription of COS V bronzes, viz. SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI. There is, however, just one type of Trajanic sestertii combining this inscription with a Pax reverse of the type described above, and it is of the utmost rarity, with currently no more than three specimens known to me.⁶ Furthermore, the object in the personification's right hand does not look like a branch (the normal attribute of Pax): to judge from autopsy, it is most probably a *patera*. Hence, I conclude that the model of this imitation was a sestertius of Trajan featuring Salus seated to the left, pouring a libation at an altar around which is entwined a serpent (**Pl. 15, 9–10**).⁷ It is true that the altar is not depicted on the Marham imitation, but a detail of its reverse image seems to settle the question. The right lower leg of the personification is strangely thin, long and curved, quite unlike representations of

⁴ B. Woytek, *Die Reichsprägung des Kaisers Traianus (98–117)*. *MIR* 14, 2 vols (Vienna, 2010) [= *MIR Traianus*], nos 8, 16, 27, 45[H], 58, 76, 89, 93[H], 107, 134, 155, 178. A later, more elaborate version shows a kneeling Dacian in front of the personification: Woytek, *MIR Traianus* 247.

⁵ As on the imitative sestertius published in Woytek, 'Further imitations', p. 103.

⁶ Woytek, *MIR Traianus* 178: Paris; Verona; Schürmann collection – now in the collection of De Nederlandsche Bank (Amsterdam).

⁷ Woytek, *MIR Traianus* 335 (reverse legend SPQR OPTIMO PRINCIPI).

human legs on imperial coins; what is more, we should not expect to see her right lower leg depicted at all, since it is always hidden behind the left leg on comparable Trajanic coin images of seated personifications. What evidently happened was that the craftsman mistook part of the snake coiled around the altar, which he saw on his model coin, for the personification's lower leg. On Trajanic *Salus sestertii*, the part of the snake visible at the altar sometimes points directly towards the right knee of the personification or even seems to touch it, as can be seen on **Pl. 15, 9–10**: hence the engraver's mistake. On Trajanic *Salus* coins, a horizontal leg brace is usually visible in the lower part of the throne, and above it folds of a cloth lying on the seating surface. On the Marham imitation, however, the die cutter chose to depict ornaments at this spot whose shape was clearly inspired by a *sella curulis*: he was obviously not perturbed by the fact that these 'legs' did not fit together with the high back of the throne.

To round off this contribution, we will present an imitative dupondius with Trajanic types that recently surfaced in the French trade. It is a hybrid, coupling a COS V obverse with a COS III reverse, and complements a specimen already discussed in *NC* 2010.

Imitative Dupondius

Obv. IMP CAES TRAIAN AVG GER DAC P M TR COS V P

Radiate bust of Trajan right (both wreath ties falling down the emperor's neck), drapery on left shoulder.

Border of dots.

Rev. (starting at 10 o'clock, retrograde) TR POT

(starting at 1 o'clock, orthodox) [COS] IIII P P

S C (in exergue)

Female personification ('Abundantia-Securitas') seated to the left on crossed *cornuacopiae*, holding short sceptre in right hand.

Border of dots.

Weight 12.20g; 6h; diameter 27mm.

Private collection, bought in April 2014 in Paris from the coin dealer Frank Lagnitree.

Pl. 15, 11

Retrograde inscriptions are rarely found on contemporary copies of Trajanic coins. The two *modius* reverse dies for sestertii of the group treated above are quite exceptional in this respect – as is the reverse die of this imitative middle bronze, whose origin is probably to be sought in France. This die is very unusual in that it combines retrograde and orthodox elements in the main legend. Hitherto, the die had been attested only on an imitative middle bronze from the Schürmann collection – one of the very few coins published by the collector himself (**Pl. 15, 12**).⁸ When the Schürmann dupondius was produced, the die was quite fresh, whereas it

⁸ De Nederlandsche Bank (Amsterdam), Schürmann coll., inv. no. 2509; provenance unknown. H. Schürmann, 'Onbekende Trajanus-munten', *Jaarboek voor Munt- en Penningkunde* 38 (1951), pp. 101–3, p. 102, no. 2 (illustrated on Schürmann's pl. VI). Also illustrated in Woytek, 'A new 'Trajanic' sestertius', pl. 10, no. 19.

appears already rather worn on the coin which turned up in France: the surface of this specimen's reverse is flat, and there is evidence for die damage in the coin's right field. The two dupondii – which are both of nearly full weight – were struck from two different obverse dies. While the newly discovered coin features a die of excellent style, the portrait on the Schürmann specimen is rather awkward-looking. It has a COS V legend like the new coin, albeit a different one, viz. IMP TR–AIANO AVG GER DAC P M TR P COS V P P. On official 'Abundantia/Securitas' dupondii of Trajan's fourth consulate, the obverse legend was IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG GERM P M.⁹

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- 2 Imitative sestertius. *NC* 2010, pl. 7, no. 2 and 2a = *NC* 2013, pl. 22, no. 2. Richard Beleson collection. Photo © Frank Kovacs.
- 3 Imitative sestertius. *NC* 2010, pl. 7, no. 3 = *NC* 2013, pl. 22, no. 3. Dr Christian Jones collection. Photo © Dr Christian Jones.
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⁹Woytek, *MIR Traianus* 96.

PLATE 14

WOYTEK, MORE IMITATIVE TRAJAN SESTERTII (1)

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8

9

10

11

12

WOYTEK, MORE IMITATIVE TRAJAN SESTERTII (2)

4a

6a

8a

WOYTEK, MORE IMITATIVE TRAJAN SESTERTII (3)

